

3 A217T, 2 F217V, 3 I217T, 1 I217V, 4 T217A, 1 T217F, 7 T217I, 1 T217L, 1 T217V, 2 V217F



0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 A217T, 2 F217V, 3 I217T, 1 I217V, 4 T217A, 1 T217F, 7 T217I, 1 T217L, 1 T217V, 2 V217F



- T
- I
- V
- {I}
- A
- L
- F

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 A217T, 2 F217V, 3 I217T, 1 I217V, 4 T217A, 1 T217F, 7 T217I, 1 T217L, 1 T217V, 2 V217F



0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 A217T, 2 F217V, 3 I217T, 1 I217V, 4 T217A, 1 T217F, 7 T217I, 1 T217L, 1 T217V, 2 V217F



- T
- I
- V
- {IT}
- A
- L
- F

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12